

of pyridine or methanol as the sixth ligand, the $O \rightarrow V \pi$ -bond is slightly affected making this discrimination. Only in the most non-interacting solvent as dichloromethane, the band $2B_2 \rightarrow 2A_1$ appears as a shoulder at $24,730 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ being observed at the low energy tail of the U.V. bands (Fig. 2B). The pyridine solution is quite unstable and the colour of the solution gradually changes from green to yellow at room temperature and ultimately, after two days, to a deep yellow solution. No $d-d$ transition band is observed in the latter solution suggesting thereby that the oxovanadium (IV) complex is decomposed in pyridine with subsequent oxidation to vanadium (V) state. The methanol solution of the complex [where the $d-d$ band is observed in the same region as in the pyridine solvent (Table 1)] also changes colour similarly but the rate is quite slow.

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Fig. 2. Electronic spectra of the complex in the visible region :
A. In methanol
B. In dichloromethane

The $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band characteristic of the N-oxide in the quinoline N-oxide molecule¹⁰ in different solvents before and after complex formation is shown in Table 2. In dichloromethane and acetonitrile solvents the hypsochromic shift characteristic of complex

TABLE 2. ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS OF $\text{VOCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$ IN HIGH ENERGY REGION

Solvents	Band position in QO (nm)	Band position in $\text{VOCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$ (nm)	Shift (nm)
Dichloromethane	338	333	5
Acetonitrile	338	336	2
Pyridine	345	345	0
Methanol	340	340	0

formation is observed though in the latter solvent the extent of this shift is lesser. But no such shifts are observed in pyridine and methanol solvents where probably solvent interaction at such a high dilution completely decomposes the complex with the liberation of the N-oxide.

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Flavonoids of Sugar-Cane

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THE dark reddish-brown peelings of sugar-cane were extracted with boiling ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated and fractionated

into (1) ether soluble fraction and (2) ethyl acetate soluble fraction. A glycoside (A) was isolated from fraction (2) and ether soluble fraction (1) gave another glycoside (B). These glycosides crystallised as homogeneous semicrystalline solids from ethyl acetate-petrol ether mixture as well as from ethanol-ether mixture. Their homogeneity was confirmed by paper chromatography and thin-layer chromatography using different solvents.

Glycoside (A) :

It was a cream coloured solid, m.p. 190-192° (decomp.), (found C, 60.1; H, 5.48; Calc. for $C_{23}H_{24}O_{10}$: C, 60.0; H, 5.22%). It gave positive Molisch test and did not reduce Fehling's solution, thereby showing its glycosidic nature. Acid hydrolysis of the glycoside yielded an aglycone, $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ and a reducing sugar which was identified as D(+)-glucose by mixed paper chromatography and osazone formation.

The pale yellowish-brown aglycone was found to be flavonoid in nature by its characteristic colour reactions. It gave yellow colour with ammonia, deep yellow colour with sodium hydroxide, yellowish-brown colour with conc. sulphuric acid, pale orange colour with magnesium-hydrochloric acid and no definite colour with ferric chloride. It was found to contain two methoxyl groups by Zeisel's method. A definite peak at 2850 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum further confirmed the presence of methoxyl group¹.

From the UV and IR spectra it was concluded that the glycoside may be apigenin derivative. Positions of the different groups were decided by taking shifts with different reagents in the ultra-violet region². No bathochromic shift of either short wave length band (II) or the long wave length band (I) with boric acid-sodium acetate in ethanol with either aglycone or glycoside suggested the absence of any catechol unit in the molecule. Both glycoside as well as aglycone did not show any shift of the short wave length band (II) with sodium acetate, thereby indicating the presence of a methoxyl group in position 7 position 5 also may be substituted with a methoxyl group, as was confirmed by no shift with aluminium chloride of any absorption band of either the glycoside or the aglycone. The only alternative left for the glucose moiety is at position 4' of the side phenyl. With sodium ethylate (0.002M) the band (I) in the aglycone shows a bathochromic shift of 53 nm, which is characteristic of the free 4' hydroxyl group.^{3,4}

Based on the above data, the following hypothetical structure (I) has been assigned to this glycoside.

Glycoside (B) :

This compound gave positive Molisch test and did not reduce Fehling's solution, thereby suggesting its glycosidic nature. On acid hydrolysis galactose and a flavonoid aglycone were obtained. Elemental analysis as well as sugar estimation of the glycoside suggested it to be a monogalactoside (Found C, 59.20; H, 5.16; Calc. for $C_{22}H_{22}O_{10}$, C, 59.19; H, 4.93%). The UV and IR spectra suggested it to be an apigenin derivative.

The aglycone was found to contain one methoxyl group (Zeisel; IR absorption peak at 2850 cm^{-1})¹. The position of the sugar entity and methoxyl group was decided by taking shifts in UV spectrum with different reagents².

No bathochromic shift was obtained with aluminium chloride in case of both, the glycoside as well as aglycone. Hence position 5 should be substituted with a methoxyl group. The aglycone gave a diacetate and the glycoside contains only one galactose unit, therefore one of the hydroxyls in either 7 or 4' positions should be free. No shift with boric acid-sodium acetate indicated absence of any catechol unit in the molecule. A conspicuous bathochromic shift of the shorter wave length band (II) in the aglycone suggested a free 7 hydroxyl group, therefore the 4' hydroxyl is likely to be substituted with the sugar moiety.

Based on this data the following hypothetical structure (II) has been assigned to this glycoside.

It is for the first time that these two flavone glycosides are being reported in sugar-cane. Although Farber⁵ *et al* have reported the presence of apigenin in this plant, none of its methyl ethers or glycosides have so far been reported.

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